

Table S1. Bycatch species from the purse-seine tuna fishery data in the Colombian Pacific Ocean from 2000 to 2019.

No.	Species	Common name
1. Teleosts		
1	<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>	Wahoo
2	<i>Aluterus cf. scriptus</i>	Scrawled Filefish
3	<i>Aluterus monoceros</i>	Unicorn Leatherjacket Filefish
4	<i>Balistes polylepis</i>	Finescale Triggerfish
5	<i>Canthidermis maculata</i>	Spotted Oceanic Triggerfish
6	<i>Caranx sexfasciatus</i>	Bigeye Trevally
7	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	Mahi-Mahi, Dolphinfinh
8	<i>Coryphaena equiselis</i>	Pompano Dolphinfinh
9	<i>Decapterus macarellus</i>	Mackerel Scad
10	<i>Diodon sp.</i>	Porcupinefish
11	<i>Elagatis bipinnulata</i>	Rainbow Runner
12	<i>Istiompax indica</i>	Black Marlin
13	<i>Istiophorus platypterus</i>	Indo-Pacific Sailfish
14	<i>Kajikia audax</i>	Striped Marlin
15	<i>Kyphosus elegans</i>	Cortez Sea Chub
16	<i>Kyphosus ocyurus</i>	Blue Stripped Chub
17	<i>Kyphosus vaigiensis</i>	Brassy Chubblue-Bronze Chub
18	<i>Lobotes pacifica</i>	Pacific Tripletail
19	<i>Makaira nigricans</i>	Blue Marlin
20	<i>Mola mola</i>	Ocean Sunfish
21	<i>Naucrates ductor</i>	Pilotfish
22	<i>Scarus rubroviolaceus</i>	Ember Parrotfish
23	<i>Seriola peruana</i>	Fortune Jack
24	<i>Seriola rivoliana</i>	Longfin Yellowtail
25	<i>Seriola lalandi</i>	Yellowtail Amberjack
26	<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i>	Shortbill Spearfish
27	<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	Swordfish
2. Elasmobranchs		
2.1. Sharks		
1	<i>Alopias pelagicus</i>	Pelagic Tresher Shark
2	<i>Alopias superciliosus</i>	Bigeye Thresher Shark
3	<i>Alopias vulpinus</i>	Common Thresher
4	<i>Carcharhinus brachyurus</i>	Copper Shark
5	<i>Carcharhinus cerdale</i>	Smalltail Shark
6	<i>Carcharhinus falciformis</i>	Silky Shark
7	<i>Carcharhinus leucas</i>	Bull Shark

8	<i>Carcharhinus limbatus</i>	Blacktip Shark
9	<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>	Oceanic Whitetip Shark
10	<i>Carcharhinus obscurus</i>	Dusky Shark
11	<i>Prionace glauca</i>	Blue shark
12	<i>Rhincodon typus</i>	Whale Shark
13	<i>Rhizoprionodon longurio</i>	Pacific Sharpnose Shark
14	<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Scalloped Hammerhead Shark
15	<i>Sphyrna mokarran</i>	Great Hammerhead Shark
16	<i>Sphyrna zygaena</i>	Smooth Hammerhead Shark
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2.2. Mantas and rays		
1	<i>Mobula mobular</i>	Spinetail Devil Ray
2	<i>Mobula munkiana</i>	Munk's Devil Ray
3	<i>Mobula tarapacana</i>	Chilean Devil Ray
4	<i>Mobula thurstoni</i>	Smoothtail Mobula
5	<i>Pteroplatytrygon violacea</i>	Pelagic Stingray
6	<i>Rhinoptera steindachneri</i>	Pacific Cownose Ray
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3. Sea turtles		
1	<i>Caretta caretta</i>	Loggerhead Sea Turtle
2	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Green Sea Turtle
3	<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	Hawksbill Sea Turtle
4	<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	Olive Ridley Sea Turtle
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4. Mollusks		
1	<i>Argonauta</i> sp.	Paper Nautilus
2	<i>Dosidicus gigas</i>	Humboldt Squid
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5. Marine mammals		
1	<i>Delphinus delphis</i>	Common Dolphin
2	<i>Stenella attenuata</i>	Pantropical Spotted Dolphin
3	<i>Stenella longirostris</i>	Spinner Dolphin
4	<i>Steno bredanensis</i>	Rough-toothed Dolphin
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